

**Instructions for repeating
Discrete Chi-Square Method (DCM) analysis
in
“Say Hello to Algol’s New Companion Candidates”
(2021, The Astrophysical Journal, XX, yy, doi xx)
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Update: Vol and page in title and references - ApjJ doi in title

Background

We highlight file names, code subroutines and code variables in **red text**. The original DCM python code `dcm.py` was published in [doi 10.5281/zenodo.3661072](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3661072). The instruction manual for this `dcm.py` code application was published in the Appendix of Jetsu (2020, hereafter **Paper I**). All instructions that were given in this manual are also valid in the current study “Say Hello to Algol’s New Companion Candidates” (Jetsu, 2021, hereafter **Paper II**).

We publish the second DCM python code version `dcm2.py` here in [doi 10.5281/zenodo.5082125](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5082125). We apply this second version `dcm2.py` in our Paper II. Here, we explain how the `dcm2.py` python code users can reproduce our main results (Paper II: Tables A6-A14).

Reproducing Paper II results

Download

- Python program code files `dcm2.py` and `fisher.py`
- Data files `1hjdAlgol.dat`, `2hjdAlgol.dat` and `3hjdAlgol.dat`
- Control files `1hjd*R*.dat`, `2hjd*R*.dat` and `3hjd*R*.dat`

to the same directory in your computer.

The name of the control file `dcm.dat` that is used to compute the results for any particular model \mathcal{M} is given on last column of every Table A6-A11. For example, the $\mathcal{M}=1$ model control file in Table A6 is `1hjd13R120S.dat`. Reproducing the DCM analysis for this $\mathcal{M}=1$ model requires only two Linux-commands

```
cp 1hjd13R120S.dat dcm.dat
python dcm2.py
```

After DCM analysis of each Table A6-A11, the Fisher test results can be obtained with `fisher.py`.

`dcm.py` bugs corrected

1. - In `dcm.py`, the linear least squares fit subroutine `LinearLSF`, and the nonlinear least squares fit subroutine `NonLinearLSF`, used weights computed from the errors of data when `TestStat \neq 1`. For `TestStat \neq 1`, the DCM test statistic is the sum of squared residuals R . Hence, the correct approach would have been to use equal weights, because R assumes unknown weights. This did not mislead our analysis in Paper I, because we analysed weighted data with known errors.
 - In `dcm2.py`, subroutines `LinearLSF` and `NonLinearLSF` are non-weighted, because the mean of all σ_i errors is used as the error estimate for every observation when `TestStat \neq 1`.
2. - In `dcm.py`, the tested frequencies of the short search could be negative in some cases when the long search interval was already close to zero frequency. This did not mislead our analysis in Paper I, because we did not test negative frequencies.
 - In `dcm2.py`, we test only positive frequencies.
3. - In `dcm.py`, we subtracted the first time point `T0= t_0` from all time points before modelling. In our figures, we never added `T0= t_0` back. This “graphical bug” did not mislead the numerical results of Paper I.
 - In `dcm2.py`, we use a polynomial trend argument that completely eliminates this `T0` problem (Paper II: Eq. 6).

`dcm2.py` improvements introduced

We use control file `1hjd14R321S.dat` to illustrate `dcm2.py` improvements.

1. `dcm2.py` produces a plot of each $h_j(t_i)$ signal, and the data values (Paper II: Eq. 20)

$$y_{i,j} = y_i - [g(t_i) - h_j(t_i)]$$

For control file `1hjd14R321S.dat`, this signals figure is `1hjd14R321SSignals.eps` (Paper II: Fig. A8).

2. `dcm2.py` produces four new additional files. For control file `1hjd14R321S.dat`, these four files are
 - `1hjd14rR321SPoints.dat` contains 11 columns and 2224 lines. The i :th line contains the following values at observing times t_i

$$t_i \quad y_i \quad \sigma_i \quad g(t_i) \quad h_1(t_i) \quad h_2(t_i) \quad h_3(t_i) \quad h_3(t_i) \quad h_5(t_i) \quad h_6(t_i) \quad p(t_i)$$

For example, columns 1-4 on line 1

`2.3722383510e+06 -1.7216000000e-01 1.0000000000e-04 -1.839251030e-01`

are $t_1 = 2372238.351$, $y_1 = -0.17216$, $\sigma_1 = 0.0001$ and $g(t_1) = -0.018392$.

Columns 8-10 on all lines give dummy values `-9.9999000000e+01` = -99.999 for the non-existent $h_4(t_i) = h_5(t_i) = h_6(t_i)$ signals.

- `1hjd14R321SCurves.dat` contains 9 columns and 5001 lines. The first column contains 5001 time points t_j evenly spaced between t_1 and t_n . The nine columns of the j :th line are

$$t_j \quad g(t_j) \quad h_1(t_j) \quad h_2(t_j) \quad h_3(t_j) \quad h_3(t_j) \quad h_5(t_j) \quad h_6(t_j) \quad p(t_j)$$

For example, columns 1-4 on line 1

`2.3722383510e+06 -1.8392510304e-01 -5.3299304230e-03 -1.3436095201e-03`

are $t_1 = 2372238.3510$, $g(t_1) = -0.18392$, $h_1(t_1) = -0.00533$ and $h_2(t_1) = -0.00134$.

Columns 6-7 on all lines give dummy values `-9.9999000000e+01` = -99.999 for the non-existent $h_4(t_j) = h_5(t_j) = h_6(t_j)$ signals.

- `1hjd14R321SPredict.dat` contains 22 columns and 21 lines. It contains the following parameters of the best DCM model

$$K_1 \quad K_2 \quad K_3 \quad t_1 \quad t_n \quad \bar{\beta}$$

where the free parameters are

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\beta} &= [\bar{\beta}_I, \bar{\beta}_{II}] \\ \bar{\beta}_I &= [f_1, f_2, f_3] \\ \bar{\beta}_{II} &= [B_{1,1}, C_{1,1}, B_{1,2}, C_{1,2}, B_{2,1}, C_{2,1}, B_{2,2}, C_{2,2}, B_{3,1}, C_{3,1}, B_{3,2}, C_{3,2}, M_0, M_1] \end{aligned}$$

The model parameters for the original data are given on line 1, while the model parameters for 20 bootstrap samples are given on lines 2-21.

For example, the original data model parameters in columns 1-5 on line 1

`3.0000000000e+00 2.0000000000e+00 1.0000000000e+00 2.3722383510e+06 2.4584097612e+06`

are $K_1 = 3$, $K_2 = 2$, $K_3 = 1$, $t_1 = 2372238.510$ and $t_n = 2458409.712$.

The frequencies in columns 6-8 on line 1

`4.9119914731e-05 4.0417872067e-05 1.2500086839e-05`

are $f_1 = 4.912 \times 10^{-5}$, $f_2 = 4.042 \times 10^{-5}$ and $f_3 = 1.250 \times 10^{-5}$. The corresponding periods are $P_1 = 20358$, $P_2 = 24742$ and $P_3 = 79999$ (Paper II: Table A7).

The last columns 21-22 on line 1

`-2.8492325178e-02 1.2781036052e-01`

give the polynomial trend $p(t)$ coefficients $M_0 = -0.02849$ and $M_1 = 0.1278$. We use the latter M_1 value in computing the long-term constant orbital period $P_{\text{orb}} = 2.^d86732870$ of Algol (Paper II: Eq. 27).

- `1hjd14R321SNotes.dat` contains notes of the following DCM analysis results:

intersecting frequencies – periods at edges of tested period intervals

For example, the only note

Long search: 3 period at edge

in `1hjd14R321SNotes.dat` means that the best period in the long search is at the edge of the tested period interval. There are no notes of intersecting frequencies.

References

- Jetsu, L. 2020, *The Open Journal of Astrophysics*, 3, 4
- . 2021, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 920, A137